

**PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FACTORS OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH
DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY EDUCATION.****Savriyeva Hurriyat Ochilovna**

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By the 60s and 70s of the 20th century, psycholinguistics began to form as an independent scientific direction, which in turn caused an increase in interest in ontolinguistics. It was around this time that ontolinguistics began to take shape as a discipline in the West. Western scientists R. Brown, D. Slobin, M. Brain, M. Bauerman and E. Clark began to seriously study the problems of ontolinguistics. Nevertheless, Western scientists have studied the research of Russian linguists in a certain sense. Western researchers relied more on the works of Russian linguists and psychologists than L.S. Vygotsky, A.R. Luria and A.N. Gvozdev. Ontolinguistics has been taught as a subject in a number of universities and colleges in Europe and the United States of America. In the following decades, Western researchers surpassed Russian scientists. Researches related to adult speech in the fields of morphology, syntax, and lexicology of linguistics have been successfully used in the study of children's speech. Not only philologists, but also psychologists began to deal with the problems of the formation of children's speech. Psychologists such as Vygotsky, Luria, Leontev, Jinkin mainly studied the development of children's speech in connection with psychological processes such as memory, imagination and attention. The contribution of the psychologist Vygotsky to the development of ontolinguistics is also of great importance. The scientist's thesis "Myshlenie i rech" published in 1937 fully explained the concept of the formation of children's speech. In his research, Vygotsky focuses more on the formation of inner speech in children. He emphasizes that inner speech in a child does not appear quickly, it appears only when a certain period of age is reached, and the process of formation of inner speech in a child ends only when the child reaches 10-11 years old. According to Vygotsky's research, 4 stages play an important role in the emergence of children's speech. These include:

1. Emergence of a motive (why does the child want to speak?)
2. Formation of thoughts (what does the child want to say?)
3. Emergence of inner speech;
4. The emergence of sentences.

By 1977, under the leadership of the Russian scientist S. N. Tseitlin, the first school of children's speech linguistics was opened in St. Petersburg. Stella

Naumovna headed the department of children's speech at the faculty of pre-school education of RDPU named after A.I.Hertsen in Russia. He also opened a children's speech laboratory. S. N. Tseitlin developed a program for the study of children's speech, which is now used in many Russian universities.

It is known that the process of children's acquisition of their native language takes place in the same way in different children who are born and grow up in different environments. Researchers name and classify the stages of child speech formation in different ways.

In addition to these, A.G. Smolensiy divided the stage into 4 and M.M. Koltsova divided into 3 stages are classified. Each of these stages greatly contributes to the thorough and perfect study of the formation periods of a child's speech.

In general, the formation of a child's speech can be divided into 4 periods:

1. The child's vocabulary is very shallow...
2. The number of words in the child's vocabulary increases very quickly.
3. Children's speech becomes more active by this time.
4. The level of language acquisition will be extremely high.

1. During this period, he imitates only external sounds, can pronounce monosyllabic words. He tries to express sounds through various gestures and actions (mimicry and gestures). During this period, the child tends to use verbs made up of repeated syllables.

2. Begins to pronounce syllables based on falling or alternating sounds. During this period, the child begins to control his own speech, observes the speech of the people around him, sometimes expresses a critical attitude towards them, and this situation gradually develops.

3. Vocabulary increases significantly. A child who initially uses words with 4-5 syllables can later pronounce words with more syllables. With the enrichment of the vocabulary content, speech thinking is also formed. The child begins to

distinguish concreteness from abstraction. At the same time, it takes over the words of all word groups.

4. All the complex aspects of grammar will be mastered. This process is unique to the speaking style. The ability to master literary language and written speech falls on children of school age.

Attention to ontolinguistics in Uzbek linguistics began in the 80s of the last century. Linguists O.Umarkhujaeva, M.Ismoilov and M.Kurbonova researches in this regard are devoted to some phonetic changes observed in the speech of Uzbek children and the psycholinguistic interpretation of children's speech.

References:

1. Hayitov H. A. Sharq mumtoz adabiyotida ohang talqini //Мировая наука. – 2019. – №. 8. – С. 3-5.
2. Ahmadovich H. H., Amrulloevna S. D. XX ASR QISSACHILIGI TARAQQIYOTIDA FOLKLORNING LATIFA JANRI TA'SIRI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 302-304.
3. Ahmadovich H. H. Expression of Folklorisms in the Works of Ghafur Ghulam //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2022. – T. 14. – С. 101-105.
4. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFLARDA O 'ZBEK QISSALARI TAHLILINING INNOVATSION USULLARI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 350-352.
5. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. O 'RXUN-YENISEY BITIKLARIDA TALIM-TARBIYA TO 'G 'RISIDAGI FIKRLARNING YORITILISHI VA ULARNING TARBIYAVIY AHAMIYATI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 349-350.
6. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. IJODIY TOPSHIRIQLAR O 'QUV MOTIVLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING SAMARALI VOSITASI SIFATIDA //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 293-294.
7. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. BOSHLANG 'ICH TA'LIMDA O 'ZLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING PSIXO-DIDAKTIK ASOSLARI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 332-334.
8. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. O 'QUVCHILARNING BILUV FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISHGA QARATILGAN DARSDAN TASHQARI ISHLAR VA ULARNI TASHKIL ETISH METODIKASI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 343-345.
9. Ahtamovich H. H., Shixnazarovna J. A. O 'QUVCHILAR O 'ZLASHTIRISH DARAJALARINI TASHHISLASH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 306-309.

10. Ahmadovich H. H., Aminovna A. S. BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFI O 'QISH DARSLARIDA DIDAKTIK O 'YIN VA INTERFAOL USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 100-102.
11. Ahmadovich H. H., Amrullojeva S. D. RUNN BITIKLARI AXLOQ VA VATANPARVARLIKNING YUKSAK NAMUNASI SIFATIDA //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 248-250.
12. Ahmadovich K. H., Bahridinovna S. G. Development and practical application of acmeological technologies of student assessment diagnose //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 6. – C. 141-145.
13. Ahmadovich K. H., Zokirovna Z. A. G. THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN EDUCATION AND MORALITY IN FOLKLORE //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – T. 25. – C. 133-137.
14. Ahmadovich K. H., Nodirkulovna A. I. Theory of Fairy Tales in Primary Grades, The Nature of the Fairy Tale Genre //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 7. – C. 130-133.
15. BuxDUPI H. A. H. et al. AKMEOLOGIYA VA UNING O'QUVCHILAR O'ZLASHTIRISHINI TASHXISLASHDAGI O'RNI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 415-417.
16. Хаитов Х. Адабиётда кулгидан фойдаланиш анъанасининг асослари //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3/5. – С. 49-52.
17. Ҳайитов Ҳ. А. ЛЎЛИ НОМИ БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ ЛАТИФАЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //Интернаука. – 2021. – №. 17-4. – С. 51-52.
18. Hayitov H. A. QUSHLARGA IBRAT-HAZRATI XIZR! //Интернаука. – 2020. – №. 12-3. – С. 72-73.
19. Khoja o'g'li T., Ahmadovich K. H. Advanced Characteristics of the Tradition of Using Uzbek Folk Humor Art in Written Literature //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 9. – C. 1-4.
20. Khaitov H., Amonova S. ЎЗБЕК ҲИКОЯ ВА ҚИССАЛАРИДА КУЛГИ МАДАНИЯТИНИНГ ИЛДИЗЛАРИ //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 140-144.

